

Quantum Interference and Statistical Mechanics Part 2

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In a previous note, we argued that a quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ is a relative conditional probability at x such that: $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp[i dx d \ln W/dx (1/i)]$ ((1)) where $\langle p \rangle_{ave} \text{ at } x = -i d/dx \ln W$ and $\langle pp \rangle_{ave} \text{ at } x = -d/dx d/dx W/W$. The latter may be utilized in an energy conservation equation to yield either the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation. $W(x)$ in general is periodic with positive and negative values. Alternatively, one may write: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which implies a particle may be in an instantaneous free momentum p state. These states “interfere” not just at the $\exp(ipx)$ level, but also when forming averages of p or $pp/2m$ because $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ and both functions take on positive and negative values. One may argue that “coarse graining” occurs removing extra information contained in the $\exp(ipx)$'s. We wish to investigate this further in this note. In particular, we wish to show that ((1)) together with $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ seems to force interference upon $\exp(ipx)$ components.

Free Quantum Particles

A free quantum particle is described by a conditional probability of $\exp(ipx)$ with $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and $-d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = pp \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ contains a periodicity which manifests itself experimentally when the particle interacts with a two slit potential, but even in that case, the two slits have to be about a wavelength apart. It seems that as the particle travels towards the two slits, it is very much classical in that it has momentum p and kinetic energy $pp/2m$ at each point x , yet at the same time tracks its phase. If one considers an ensemble of such free particles in a bound state, one may ask: Why would kinetic energy “interfere” in such an ensemble if each member has $pp/2m$ at each point:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } pp/2m \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Note that $p/-p$ pairs with $a(p)=a(-p)$ yield $\cos(px)$ terms which are positive in some places and negative in others. If $\exp(ipx)$ represents a free particle, the kinetic energy should be $pp/2m$ at each x and it seems there is no reason for interference. Given that interference does occur, it seems some extra “information” linked with free particles $\exp(ipx)$ is removed in order to create the wavefunction $W(x)$. Thus it seems, constraints on the wavefunction should be compared to ideas associated with free particles $\exp(ipx)$.

First, assume each free particle has a kinetic energy $pp/2m$ which does not interfere i.e.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } pp/2m \text{ } a(p,x)] / W1(x) \text{ with } W1(x) \text{ with } a(p,x) > 0 \quad ((2b))$$

In a bound system there exists one particle, so if it is in a state p , it is not another momentum state. One does not have various momentum states interfering at the same time. Second,

consider that average kinetic energy must change according to $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)= E$. Then it seems that $1/W(x)$ in ((1)) must change as average kinetic energy because one assumes ((2b)). (Here one assumes that $a(p,x)=a(p,x+dx)$ because a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ does not change its kinetic energy moving from x to $x+dx$ even though it picks up a phase.)

Thus:

$$KE_{ave}(x) / KE_{ave}(x+dx) = W_1(x+dx) / W_1(x) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Or } 1 + dx \frac{d \ln W_1}{dx} = (E-V(x)) / \{ (E-V(x)) - dx \frac{dV}{dx} \} \quad ((4))$$

((4)), however, violates ((1)) which suggests that:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \quad ((1))$$

In other words, $W_1(x)$ is not equal to $W(x)$ or the constraint of ((1)) on the wavefunction does not allow the $pp/2m$ kinetic energies of free particles to add without interference. Interference must occur if one uses ((1)) and ((2)) together with $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x) = E$. Thus, ((1)) seems to be a strong constraint on the wavefunction. It should be noted that $W(x)$ has experimental confirmation from spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ that there is a resolution pattern or positive/negative humps in many cases.

The fact that interference occurs is not surprising given that $W(x)$ is treated as a probability that adds in "or" situations. As argued in previous notes, for an incoming quantum particle flux $A \exp(ipx)$ which scatters off a potential, the total wavefunction is:

$$W_{total}(x) = A \exp(ipx) + f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r \quad ((5))$$

The two terms on the RHS must interfere so that some probability flux is removed from $A \exp(ipx)$ to account for scattered particles.

In the case of ((2)), some information associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and its kinetic energy is removed at certain x spots, so the overall $W(x)$ is a kind of "coarse-grained" object with its own positive and negative humps created by removing some information from $\exp(ipx)$'s. Unlike the case of ((5)), one would not necessarily have expected such interference using a single free particle ensemble to model a bound particle.

It should be further noted that one does not really have free particles in ((2)), rather one has:

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((6))$$

at each x point. In other words, the normalization constant associated with each "free" $\exp(ipx)$ changes with x which is something different than for a general quantum free particle which is simply represented by $\exp(ipx)$.

Constraint of $-i\hbar/dx \ln W = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ and Impact on Interference

We have argued above that interference of $\exp(ipx)$'s must occur (even when taking averages of $pp/2m$) due to: $-i\hbar/dx \ln W = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ ((1)). This in turn leads to $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W/W + V(x)=E$ ((7)) which may be used to solve for W .

Thus, somehow this constraint must lead to a loss of information regarding single free $\exp(ipx)$'s/.

One may first note that ((1)) implies $-i\hbar/dx \ln W$ be nonzero, otherwise there is no phase change as one moves from x to $x+dx$. If $a(p)=a(-p)$ and there is no interference, then the probability to have p and $-p$ is the same i.e. one uses $|\exp(ipx)|$ and $|\exp(-ipx)|$ yielding an average p of 0, just as in classical statistical mechanics. This violates the idea of a phase change, even in a bound system. In quantum mechanics, $-i\hbar/dx \ln W$ is not zero, but this is due to interference and already manifests itself for a $p/-p$ pair which yields, for $a(p)=a(-p)$:

$$P \text{ relative ave for } +/p = i2p a(p) \sin(px) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is zero at the zeros of $\sin(px)$ and zero on average, just not at every x point. In fact, there is characteristic length, the wavelength $\lambda = 2\pi/p$ which defines the range over which P relative ave (for $+/-p$) averages to 0. For high p values, this length becomes smaller and smaller, approaching the classical idea of P ave ($+/-p$) being zero for more and more x points. Thus, it seems that "fluctuations" appear in ((7)). These are of a physical nature because ultimately $W(x)$ has positive/negative humps just as $\sin(px)$ which are observable in the spatial density. These define a "resolution" in the bound system which is a kind of average of the resolution of the single free $\exp(ipx)$ resolutions. The single free $\exp(ipx)$ terms tend to "interfere" in order to create a new resolution scheme for $W(x)$, but this interference carries over to averages of kinetic energy e.g. ((2)). This is an unusual idea because it suggests there is a fluctuation scheme present in ((7)) which not only removes probability but momentum and kinetic energy in a certain range of each wavelength and adds it in another range. For a free particle with $\exp(ipx)$ there is no apparent fluctuation scheme as one has p and $pp/2m$ at each x point. One states that a free particle has p and $pp/2m$ at each x point, but given that $\exp(ipx)$ tracks phase and is sensitive over the same wavelength range, it may be that even for the free particle there is special length=wavelength and one may be assuming a fixed p and $pp/2m$ over this range.

In other words, it seems that in the statistical picture of a bound quantum state, one only has partial information about single particle states in the sense that their presence fluctuates (i.e. probability, p and $pp/2m$) for each $p/-p$ state. For example, for $a(p)=a(-p)$, probability fluctuates as $2a(p)\cos(px)$, momentum as $-2ipa(p)\sin(px)$ and kinetic energy as $pp/2m + 2a(p)\cos(px)$. This seems to indicate a loss of "information" in a bound system regarding single particles which does not happen in a classical statistical mechanical gas. For a classical gas, p average is 0 at each x point. There are no fluctuations at the average velocity or kinetic energy level (although

usual fluctuations do occur). The various different fluctuations associated with $\exp(ipx)$'s and their wavelengths "interfere" to create a new overall resolution scheme (positive and negative humps) in $W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, unlike in a classical statistical system, a quantum bound system described in terms of an ensemble of "free" particles i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ loses "information" regarding these single particle states in creating an overall $W(x)$ which satisfies: $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = \exp[i (-i\hbar/dx \ln W)]$ and $\langle pp \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -\hbar^2/dx^2 \ln W$. This loss of information seems to be synonymous with interference. Each p - p combination forms an average momentum of $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \ln W$ for $a(p) = a(-p)$ which is zero on average over a length called the wavelength, unlike classical statistical mechanics in which it is zero at each x point. For many different $\exp(ipx)$'s, one has many different wavelengths, yet must create a new overall resolution scheme (positive and negative humps) for $W(x)$. This resolution scheme is analogous to a new "wavelength" for $W(x)$ (although it is not equal to a constant value).

The new resolution scheme for $W(x)$ follows from the solution of the Schrodinger equation: $-\hbar^2/2m \langle pp \text{ ave at } x \rangle + V(x) = E$. In other words, in quantum mechanics when one adds wavefunctions (whether they be $a(p)\exp(ipx)$'s or $W_i(x)$ for certain distinguishable states or paths) one loses some of this distinguishability due to interference, but ultimately gains a new "resolution scheme" for $W_{\text{total}}(x)$ which follows $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp[i (-i\hbar/dx \ln W)]$.